

Flavour and precision probes of a class of scotogenic models

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Abstract

We address the phenomenological impact of a well-motivated class of scotogenic models regarding flavour and electroweak precision observables. For the case of a “T1-2-A” variant, we carry out a full computation of the next-to-leading order corrections to leptonic Higgs and Z -boson decays. We revisit previously drawn conclusions on operator dominance and constraints on the parameter space in view of the evolution regarding Δa_μ . Finally, we consider the role of $H \rightarrow \mu\mu$ decays (and other flavour conserving Higgs decays), as well as precision observables in probing this class of models at future colliders.

1 Introduction

Despite its many successes, the Standard Model (SM) fails to explain several observations: neutrino oscillations, the baryon asymmetry of the Universe (BAU) and its abundance of cold dark matter (DM).

Many well motivated extensions of the SM have been proposed to address these experimental caveats while also trying to ease theoretical issues. Among these new physics (NP) proposals, “scotogenic” models are especially appealing, as they generate neutrino masses radiatively (at loop level) while providing a viable DM candidate stabilised by a discrete symmetry. Departing from the original minimal model [1–3], numerous variants have been proposed - most aiming at enhancing the testability potential (for instance via charged lepton flavour violation (cLFV) [4–12] or lepton number violation (LNV) [13–16]), further considering the prospects for leptogenesis. A recent variant - the so-called “T1-2-A” setup - extends the SM via 1 (2) $SU(2)_L$ doublet and 1 (2) singlet scalar (fermions) to potentially address neutrino masses, DM, BAU through leptogenesis and the discrepancy in the anomalous magnetic moment of the muon (Δa_μ) [17]. Notice however that recently, the formerly significant tension in Δa_μ (around 5σ , relying on a data-driven computation of the hadronic vacuum polarisation contribution) [18] has been dramatically reduced to around 1σ in view of the evolution of first-principle computations of the hadronic contributions [19–28].

In [29], a thorough study of cLFV and electroweak precision observables (EWPO) was carried out, taking into account the recent evolution in Δa_μ ; particular emphasis was given to the role of EWPO, which can provide significant constraints to NP models featuring extensions of the lepton sector [30] - especially given the high precision of current and future measurements (as in the case of FCC-ee, in its Z -pole run).

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2 Brief description of the model

We consider the model first explored in [17], which introduces new fields as summarised in Table 1.

Field	η	S	F_1	F_2	Ψ_1	Ψ_2
$SU(2)_L$	2	1	1	1	2	2
$U(1)_Y$	1	0	0	0	-1	1

Table 1: Additional field content of the “T1-2-A” scotogenic model variant (cf. [17]). All fields are odd under the new Z_2 symmetry.

The SM interaction Lagrangian is generalised as follows,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{L}_{\text{fermion}} &= i(\bar{\psi}_i \gamma^\mu D_\mu \psi_i + \bar{F}_i \gamma^\mu D_\mu F_i) \\
 &\quad - M_\psi \bar{\psi}_1 \tilde{\psi}_2 - \frac{1}{2} M_{F_{ii}} \bar{F}_i^c F_i + y_{1i}^* \bar{F}_i \Phi^\dagger \tilde{\psi}_1 + y_{2i}^* \bar{F}_i \Phi \psi_2^c \\
 &\quad - g_\psi^\alpha \tilde{\psi}_2 L_L^\alpha S - g_{F_i}^\alpha \tilde{L}_L^\alpha \eta F_i - g_R^\alpha \bar{e}_R^\alpha \eta^\dagger \Psi_1 + \text{H.c.}, \tag{1}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{V}_{\text{scalar}} &= \frac{1}{2} M_S^2 S^2 + \frac{1}{2} \lambda_{4S} S^4 + M_\eta^2 |\eta|^2 + \lambda_{4\eta} |\eta|^4 + \frac{1}{2} \lambda_S S^2 |H|^2 + \frac{1}{2} \lambda_{S\eta} S^2 |\eta|^2 \\
 &\quad + \lambda_\eta |\eta|^2 |H|^2 + \lambda'_\eta |\eta H^\dagger|^2 + \frac{1}{2} \lambda''_\eta \left[(H\eta^\dagger)^2 + \text{H.c.} \right] + \alpha S [H\eta^\dagger + \text{H.c.}]. \tag{2}
 \end{aligned}$$

As common to all scotogenic realisations, the discrete Z_2 symmetry ensuring the stability of the lightest neutral NP particle precludes neutrino mass generation at the tree-level; loop-level generation (cf. Fig. 1), together with the smallness of the new couplings thus allows for a more natural explanation of neutrino masses and oscillation data in general. In turn, this gives rise

Figure 1: One-loop diagrams contributing to neutrino masses (in the interaction basis).

to contributions to the neutrino masses of the form $\bar{\nu}_\beta^c (\mathcal{M}_\nu)_{\beta\alpha} \nu_\alpha$; the neutrino mass matrix can be cast in a compact manner relying on a generalised matrix of “couplings” \mathcal{G} , and on the contributions arising from the exchange of the new massive fields in the loop, \mathcal{M}_L [17]:

$$\mathcal{M}_\nu = \mathcal{G}^T \mathcal{M}_L \mathcal{G}, \quad \text{where} \quad \mathcal{G} = \begin{pmatrix} g_\psi^e & g_\psi^\mu & g_\psi^\tau \\ g_{F_1}^e & g_{F_1}^\mu & g_{F_1}^\tau \\ g_{F_2}^e & g_{F_2}^\mu & g_{F_2}^\tau \end{pmatrix}. \tag{3}$$

Sizable cLFV couplings are encoded in \mathcal{G} , leading to a rich phenomenology. The model puts forward several DM candidates, including the lightest CP-even scalar ϕ_1 , the CP-odd scalar A^0 and the lightest fermion χ_1^0 , provided that they lead to a viable relic density [31] and comply

with constraints arising from numerous direct and indirect DM searches. To do so, we rely on micrOMEGAs [32], which provides a full evaluation of the dark matter prospects of a given NP model.

3 Flavour and electroweak observables in the scotogenic “T1-2-A” variant

As briefly mentioned in the Introduction, the tension in Δa_μ has been dramatically reduced tension (to around 1σ), and as such noticeable changes are expected to occur in the phenomenology of cLFV decays. Following comprehensive scans of the parameter space, the updated prospects for cLFV observables are displayed in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Predicted rates for $\mu \rightarrow 3e$ (top) and $\mu - e$ conversion in nuclei (bottom), both versus $\text{BR}(\mu \rightarrow e\gamma)$. On the left panels, all displayed points lead to a SM-like $(g - 2)_\mu$ (i.e. $\Delta a_\mu \approx 1.5\sigma$), while the right panels exhibit a significant NP contribution ($\Delta a_\mu \approx 4.2\sigma$). Red points denote exclusion due to conflict with dark matter constraints, grey points correspond to the violation of at least one phenomenological bound (flavour, EWPO) other than those under study; blue points are viable under all constraints but those under consideration. Full (dashed) lines correspond to current bounds (future sensitivity), with hatched areas already excluded.

The top plots of Fig. 2 display the effect of reducing the tension in Δa_μ on the apparent correlation between $\text{BR}(\mu \rightarrow 3e)$ and $\text{BR}(\mu \rightarrow e\gamma)$: a SM-like Δa_μ leads to a loss of correlation between the observables, albeit recovered when applying experimental constraints; the correlation has a strong experimental interest as the measurement of one cLFV observable inevitably predicts the observation of the other. A similar effect can be seen in the bottom row for the cLFV $\mu - e$ conversion in nuclei. These effects can be explained via the increase of the Z -Penguin contributions for a SM-like Δa_μ (compared to dominant γ -penguins for NP-like Δa_μ).

In view of the potential of future lepton colliders in what concerns EW precision, addressing the impact of a given NP model regarding the latter becomes important. While invisible decay

channels of the Z and the Higgs constrain the NP states to be heavier than $m_{Z,H}/2$, corrections to flavour conserving Z and Higgs decays offer non-trivial constraints.

Figure 3: $\text{BR}(Z \rightarrow \mu\mu)$ as a function of the scalar trilinear coupling α . Point-colour scheme as in Fig. 2. From darker to lighter, the green bands denote current bounds at 1σ , 2σ and 3σ . The full orange line corresponds to the SM 2-loop prediction [33], while dashed grey lines denote future sensitivity at FCC-ee. The left (right) panel corresponds to a SM-like (NP-like) $(g-2)_\mu$.

Figure 4: $\text{BR}(H \rightarrow \mu\mu)$ as a function of the lightest scalar mass, M_{ϕ_1} , for a SM-like $(g-2)_\mu$ (left) and a significant tension ($\Delta a_\mu = 4.2\sigma$, on the right). Line and colour code as in Fig. 3, with the full line denoting the SM prediction [34].

The results for corrections in Z (Higgs) flavour conserving decays are presented in Fig. 3 (Fig. 4). Regimes corresponding to a large trilinear coupling $\alpha \gtrsim 1$ TeV (or equivalently to a small mass for the lightest scalar $M_{\phi_1} \lesssim 1$ TeV) can lead to sizeable corrections already excluded by current experiments (especially $H \rightarrow \ell_\alpha \ell_\alpha$). Although relaxing the tension in Δa_μ mitigates the important corrections in the latter regimes, these remain largely disfavoured. Concerning the impact for lepton flavour universality violation (LFUV), notice that \mathcal{G} matrix can also induce them, but the new effects remain too small to be measured. Finally NP corrections to the S , T and U parameters were also investigated but played a non-constraining role on the parameter space (although corrections within future reach are possible).

4 Conclusions

The ‘‘T1-2-A’’ scotogenic framework remains theoretically appealing as it connects radiative neutrino mass generation with a viable dark matter candidate. In this work we have put forward the consequences of relaxing the tension in the muon $g-2$ on cLFV observables, putting forward the correlation between the observables rendering this model easily testable. We also investigated NP corrections to EWPO, leading to sizeable corrections to Z and Higgs flavour conserving decays, making $Z/H \rightarrow \mu\mu, \tau\tau$ decays prime probes for this model.

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